

Cobalt-, Nickel- and Copper(II) Complexes with
Aniline Schiff Bases

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The survey of literature reveals voluminous documentation on Schiff bases derived from anilines. But no attempt has been made to study the chelating behaviour of the Schiff bases derived from the condensation of 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydodiphenyl and substituted anilines.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes synthesised are amorphous or microcrystalline in nature and are stable in air. The analytical data (Table 1) indicate 1:2 stoichiometry of the type CuL_2Cl_2 and ML_2 [$\text{M} = \text{Ni}$ and Co], and conductivity data in DMF (10^{-3} M) indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

The Cu^{II} complexes exhibit magnetic moments in the range 1.1–1.4 B.M. indicating square-planar geometry around Cu^{II} ion^{1,2}. The Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic in nature. Hence, square-planar geometry may be proposed to the Ni^{II} complexes. The Co^{II} complexes possess magnetic moments of the order 4.2–4.5 B.M. suggesting tetrahedral geometry.

In the ir spectra of the ligands, the band due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded $\text{OH}^{3,4}$ is observed at 2800 cm^{-1} . This band was absent in the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, indicating coordination through deprotonated phenolic OH group. In the Cu^{II} complexes, the same band was observed around 3300 cm^{-1} , suggesting non-participating of OH group in coordination

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Ligand no.	Complex	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$
		M	N	Cl	
I	CuL_2Cl_2	8.39 (8.47)	3.57 (3.74)	9.35 (9.47)	10.2
	NiL_2	8.59 (8.71)	3.98 (4.16)	—	8.5
	CoL_2	8.71 (8.74)	3.96 (4.16)	—	15.2
II	CuL_2Cl_2	7.46 (7.58)	3.23 (3.34)	8.35 (8.47)	10.0
	NiL_2	7.58 (7.70)	3.45 (3.67)	—	12.5
	CoL_2	7.62 (7.72)	3.49 (3.67)	—	18.0
III	CuL_2Cl_2	8.79 (8.96)	3.90 (3.96)	9.89 (10.02)	20.0
	NiL_2	9.19 (9.28)	4.09 (4.42)	—	12.8
	CoL_2	9.24 (9.31)	4.11 (4.42)	—	10.5
IV	CuL_2Cl_2	8.49 (8.58)	3.72 (3.78)	9.48 (9.59)	15.4
	NiL_2	8.69 (8.83)	3.99 (4.22)	—	6.8
	CoL_2	8.68 (8.86)	3.02 (4.22)	—	6.9
V	CuL_2Cl_2	8.14 (8.24)	3.72 (3.64)	9.15 (9.25)	14.8
	NiL_2	8.19 (8.45)	3.93 (4.04)	—	10.0
	CoL_2	8.32 (8.48)	3.86 (4.04)	—	8.9
VI	CuL_2Cl_2	7.59 (7.70)	2.62 (3.40)	8.48 (8.61)	18.0
	NiL_2	7.72 (7.84)	3.45 (3.74)	—	9.5
	CoL_2	7.79 (7.87)	3.60 (3.74)	—	10.4

with Cu^{II} ions. The band due to C=N stretch ($1650\text{--}1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the free ligands⁵ underwent a negative shift ($10\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$) on complexation, suggesting coordination via azomethine group. The negative shift of the band indicates weakening of C-N link. Phenolic C-O stretch was observed at $1300\text{--}1260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the ligands. In the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, these bands appeared at higher wavenumber in the region $1340\text{--}1310\text{ cm}^{-1}$, confirming coordination through deprotonated phenolic OH. In the Cu^{II} complexes this band remained unchanged. In addition, ligand-VI exhibited a band at 1710 cm^{-1} due to C=O stretch and it remained unchanged on complexation. In the far-ir spectra of all the complexes, the non-ligand bands observed at $510\text{--}480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to M-N stretch⁶. The M-O stretching bands⁷ are assigned at $470\text{--}440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The bands at $270\text{--}240\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to M-Cl stretch⁸ in the Cu^{II} complexes. Hence, it can be concluded that the ligands behave as monodentate in the Cu^{II} complexes and as bidentate in the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes.

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMF (10^{-3} M) and for a few complexes in pyridine. The ligand field parameters such as Dq , B' , β , $\beta\%$ and LFSE were calculated using Underhill and Billing equation.

The Co^{II} complexes exhibited only two bands at $8300\text{--}7000$ and $16000\text{--}15800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be due to spin-allowed ν_2 and ν_3 transitions respectively. The ligand field parameters Dq ($452\text{--}495\text{ cm}^{-1}$), B' ($633\text{--}778\text{ cm}^{-1}$), β ($0.65\text{--}0.80$), $\beta\%$ ($19.54\text{--}34.53$) and LFSE ($15.50\text{--}16.97\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) are indicative of tetrahedral geometry for the Co^{II} complexes.

The electronic spectra of square-planar Ni^{II} complexes are difficult to interpret due to the fact that the relative energies of the d -orbitals in such complexes are not known with certainty. However, there is every likelihood that square-planar geometry may undergo configurational change to

octahedral geometry in the environment of donor solvents. The solution state (DMF) spectra of the present Ni^{II} complexes exhibit two bands at $17540\text{--}16129$ and $25000\text{--}21740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively^{9,10}, indicating square-planar geometry. To confirm this, electronic spectra of these complexes were also recorded in pyridine. In pyridine, these complexes exhibited two bands at $14290\text{--}13510$ and $26320\text{--}24390\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the calculated ligand field parameters Dq ($806\text{--}852\text{ cm}^{-1}$), B' ($865\text{--}1003\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and LFSE ($27.63\text{--}29.21\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) indicate octahedral geometry.

The Cu^{II} complexes exhibited a broad envelop at $22200\text{--}15380\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The square-planar Cu^{II} complexes can be distinguished from tetrahedral complexes, as the latter exhibit a narrow band below 10000 cm^{-1} . As no such band was observed, tetrahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral geometry is ruled out for the present Cu^{II} complexes. However, in pyridine, these complexes exhibited a broad band at $16950\text{--}11760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating configurational change from square-planar to octahedral.

Based on the above discussion, tetrahedral structure is proposed to the Co^{II} complexes and square-planar geometry to the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes.

Experimental

4-Hydroxy-3-aldehydodiphenyl was prepared from 4-hydroxydiphenyl by the reported method¹¹. Schiff bases were prepared by refluxing substituted aniline with 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydodiphenyl in ethanolic medium for about 2 h. The reaction mixture on partial evaporation yielded the required Schiff bases : (I) with *p*-chloroaniline ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{NOCl}$, m.p. 164°), (II) *p*-bromoaniline ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{NOBr}$, 173°), (III) *p*-toluidine ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$, 127°), (IV) *p*-anisidine ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$, 160°), (V) *p*-nitroaniline ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$, 180°) and (VI) *p*-aminoethylbenzoate ($\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_3$, 147°).

Preparation of complexes : A mixture of the metal chloride (0.01 mol) and the Schiff base (0.02 mol) was refluxed in absolute ethanol for about 2 h. The separated complexes were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride. In the case of the Ni^{II} complexes alcoholic ammonia was added to isolate the compounds.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature using Gouy method. Conductivity was measured on an Elico CI-82T conductivity bridge. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF (10^{-3} M) on an Elico CI-24 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (nujol) on Hitachi 270-50 spectrophotometer.

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